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Research Article

**MOLECULAR STRUCTURE, MULLIKEN AND HOMO-LUMO
ANALYSIS OF 1,2,4-TRIAZOLO[3,4-B]-1,3,4-THIADIAZINE
BENZENESULFONAMIDE DERIVATIVES BASED ON DFT
CALCULATIONS**Tahar Abbaz^{1*}, Amel Bendjeddou¹ and Didier Villemin²

¹Laboratory of Aquatic and Terrestrial Ecosystems, Org. and Bioorg. Chem. Group, University of Mohamed-Cherif Messaadia, Souk Ahras, 41000, Algeria., ²Laboratory of Molecular and Thio-Organic Chemistry, UMR CNRS 6507, INC3M, FR 3038, Labex EMC3, ensicaen & University of Caen, Caen 14050, France.

Abstract:

Quantum chemical calculations on the geometric parameters, molecular electrostatic potential, natural bond orbital, mulliken atomic charges and nonlinear optical property of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4** were performed using the density functional theory (DFT/B3LYP) methods with 6-31G (d,p) basis set. In MEP analysis, the negative charge covers the sulfamide function and the positive region is over the hydrogen atoms. The frontier orbital energy gap and dipole moment illustrates the high reactivity of the compound **4**. The results of natural bond orbital show that the electron density (ED) is in the σ^* and π^* anti-bonding orbitals, the second order delocalization energies (E2) confirm the occurrence of intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) within the molecule. The calculated first hyperpolarizability of compound **1** is around one and half times that the value of the standard NLO material urea.

Keywords: sulfamide; density functional theory; computational chemistry; quantum chemical calculations.

Corresponding author:**Tahar Abbaz,**

Laboratory of Aquatic and Terrestrial Ecosystems,

Org. and Bioorg. Chem. Group,

University of Mohamed-Cherif Messaadia, Souk Ahras, 41000, Algeria.

E-mail: tahar.abbaz@univ-soukahras.dz

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INTRODUCTION:

The chemistry of sulfonamides is of interest as they show distinct physical, chemical and biological properties. Sulfonamides are still widely used pharmacological agents for the treatment or prevention of a variety of diseases, such as antimicrobial drugs, antithyroid agents, antitumour, antibiotics and inhibitors of carbonic anhydrase as antiglaucoma agents [1-3]. Benzenesulfonamide derivatives are used as effective inhibitors in the treatment of proliferative diseases as cancer, apoplexy, heart failure, cystic fibrosis, hepatomegaly, etc. Benzenesulfonamide moiety is an integral part of many drugs and drug-like scaffolds [4,5].

Density functional theory (DFT) approaches, especially those using hybrid fundamental have evolved to a powerful and very reliable tool, being routinely used for the determination of various molecular properties. B3LYP functional has been previously shown to provide an excellent compromise between accuracy and computational efficiency of vibrational spectra for large and medium size molecules [6-8].

In the present paper, we present a detailed study of various aspects of the 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-

thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4** reported in the literature [9] using density functional theory (DFT) and B3LYP method with 6-31G (d,p) basis set. we give a complete description of the molecular geometry, electronic transitions, global reactivity descriptors, MEP, Mulliken atomic charges, intramolecular interactions and NLO features of these series of molecules.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

All the quantum chemical calculations are carried out with Gaussian 09W program package [10] using DFT level of theory, B3LYP functional and 6-31G (d,p) as basis set.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Molecular Geometry

Figure 1 shows the optimized structures of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4** with atom numbering scheme. The optimized geometrical parameters bond length, bond angle and dihedral angle of title compounds were determined by B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) method and tabulated in Table 1-4.

Figure 1. Optimized molecular structure of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4**

Table 1. Optimized geometric parameters of compound **1**

Bond Length(Å)		Bond Angles (°)		Dihedral Angles (°)	
R(1,6)	1.396	A(2,1,6)	120.737	D(6,1,2,7)	178.215
R(4,11)	1.398	A(2,1,13)	119.805	D(13,1,2,3)	179.932
R(6,10)	1.084	A(5,4,11)	118.107	D(2,1,13,14)	154.263
R(11,12)	1.012	A(1,6,10)	119.954	D(6,1,13,16)	87.042
R(11,19)	1.333	A(12,11,19)	121.799	D(1,2,3,8)	179.848
R(13,14)	1.467	A(1,13,14)	107.806	D(2,3,4,11)	179.684
R(13,16)	1.698	A(14,13,15)	122.430	D(3,4,5,9)	179.174
R(16,17)	1.017	A(17,16,18)	111.077	D(1,13,16,17)	110.742
R(19,20)	1.292	A(11,19,20)	124.926	D(15,13,16,18)	118.246
R(20,21)	1.484	A(19,20,21)	130.045	D(11,19,20,23)	174.476
R(20,23)	1.804	A(20,21,28)	124.897	D(23,20,21,28)	29.511
R(21,24)	1.513	A(23,22,32)	128.682	D(20,21,24,27)	161.137
R(24,25)	1.099	A(21,28,29)	118.413	D(21,28,29,30)	169.544
R(30,31)	1.080	A(22,29,28)	130.171	D(22,29,30,31)	179.068
R(32,33)	1.397	A(29,30,31)	122.385	D(28,29,30,33)	175.494

Table 2. Optimized geometric parameters of compound 2

Bond Length(Å)		Bond Angles (°)		Dihedral Angles (°)	
R(1,2)	1.399	A(2,1,6)	120.542	D(11,1,6,5)	179.478
R(1,6)	1.393	A(2,1,11)	119.667	D(2,1,11,13)	163.541
R(1,11)	1.786	A(3,4,17)	116.666	D(1,2,3,8)	178.983
R(6,10)	1.084	A(4,5,9)	120.719	D(3,4,17,19)	169.269
R(11,13)	1.467	A(1,11,12)	108.083	D(4,5,6,10)	179.361
R(11,14)	1.698	A(13,11,14)	108.552	D(9,5,6,1)	178.529
R(14,15)	1.017	A(18,17,19)	106.863	D(1,11,14,15)	132.973
R(21,28)	1.294	A(21,20,23)	117.028	D(12,11,14,16)	140.756
R(22,23)	1.752	A(20,21,28)	124.349	D(17,19,20,23)	176.604
R(22,31)	1.303	A(20,23,22)	96.907	D(19,20,23,22)	149.457
R(24,25)	1.092	A(21,24,26)	110.859	D(20,21,24,27)	160.352
R(28,29)	1.364	A(22,29,28)	129.323	D(28,21,24,25)	104.686
R(29,30)	1.388	A(29,30,32)	109.208	D(23,22,29,30)	175.312
R(31,32)	1.398	A(32,30,33)	127.141	D(21,28,29,30)	170.676
R(33,34)	1.095	A(35,33,36)	109.415	D(32,30,33,34)	114.665

Table 3. Optimized geometric parameters of compound 3

Bond Length(Å)		Bond Angles (°)		Dihedral Angles (°)	
R(1,2)	1.399	A(6,1,11)	119.814	D(6,1,2,7)	178.469
R(1,6)	1.393	A(1,6,5)	120.058	D(11,1,6,5)	179.562
R(6,10)	1.084	A(1,6,10)	119.679	D(2,1,11,13)	163.231
R(11,12)	1.466	A(1,11,12)	108.029	D(1,2,3,8)	178.996
R(11,14)	1.698	A(12,11,13)	122.292	D(2,3,4,17)	179.821
R(14,15)	1.017	A(12,11,14)	105.611	D(3,4,17,19)	168.989
R(21,24)	1.509	A(15,14,16)	111.033	D(9,5,6,1)	178.443
R(22,23)	1.753	A(4,17,19)	122.434	D(12,11,14,16)	140.063
R(28,29)	1.365	A(19,20,21)	130.036	D(17,19,20,23)	176.774
R(29,30)	1.390	A(20,21,24)	120.200	D(20,21,24,27)	159.590
R(30,32)	1.308	A(20,23,22)	96.718	D(23,22,29,30)	175.093
R(31,32)	1.398	A(22,29,28)	129.045	D(28,29,30,32)	171.430
R(33,34)	1.098	A(29,30,32)	108.966	D(29,30,33,35)	163.524
R(33,39)	1.543	A(30,32,31)	108.843	D(32,30,33,39)	105.008
R(39,40)	1.095	A(35,33,39)	111.667	D(39,33,35,38)	177.864

Table 4. Optimized geometric parameters of compound 4

Bond Length(Å)		Bond Angles (°)		Dihedral Angles (°)	
R(1,11)	1.786	A(2,1,6)	120.555	D(6,1,2,7)	178.439
R(2,7)	1.084	A(1,2,3)	119.491	D(11,1,6,5)	179.297
R(11,13)	1.467	A(2,3,8)	119.993	D(2,1,11,13)	163.819
R(14,15)	1.017	A(1,11,14)	103.535	D(3,4,17,19)	172.223
R(17,18)	1.014	A(12,11,14)	105.541	D(9,5,6,1)	178.374
R(17,19)	1.391	A(4,17,18)	110.967	D(1,11,14,15)	133.197
R(19,20)	1.286	A(17,19,20)	120.072	D(12,11,14,16)	141.041
R(21,24)	1.509	A(20,21,24)	120.020	D(17,19,20,23)	176.602
R(22,23)	1.752	A(20,21,28)	124.230	D(19,20,23,22)	147.099
R(22,29)	1.383	A(29,22,31)	111.094	D(28,21,24,25)	103.999
R(24,25)	1.092	A(20,23,22)	96.398	D(23,22,29,30)	175.591
R(30,33)	1.466	A(28,29,30)	126.442	D(28,29,30,32)	167.854
R(31,32)	1.386	A(30,33,34)	123.304	D(32,30,33,34)	160.052
R(33,35)	1.407	A(30,33,35)	117.488	D(30,33,35,38)	178.823
R(34,37)	1.083	A(34,36,41)	119.418	D(35,38,40,43)	179.908

Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP)

The molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) is related to the electronic density which is a very useful descriptor for determining sites for electrophilic attack and nucleophilic reactions as well as hydrogen-bonding interactions [11,12]. To predict

reactive sites for electrophilic and nucleophilic attack for the title molecules, MEP is calculated at the B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) optimized geometries. The negative (red) regions of MEP are related to electrophilic reactivity and the positive (blue) regions to nucleophilic reactivity are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Molecular electrostatic potential surface of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4**

The regions exhibiting the negative electrostatic potential are localized on sulfamide function for compound **1** and 31N, 32N of [1,2,4]-triazole for compounds **2**, **3** and **4**; while the regions presenting the positive potential are localized vicinity of the hydrogen atoms in all molecules.

Basin analysis

The concept of basin was first introduced by Bader in his atom in molecular (AIM) theory, after that, this concept was transplant to the analysis of ELF by

Savin and Silvi. In fact, basin can be defined for any real space function, such as molecular orbital, electron density difference, electrostatic potential and even Fukui function.

A real space function in general has one or more maxima, which are referred to as attractors or (3,-3) critical points. Each basin is a subspace of the whole space, and uniquely contains an attractor. The basins are separated with each other by interbasin surfaces (IBS), which are essentially the zero-flux surface of

the real space functions; mathematically, such surfaces consist of all of the points \mathbf{r} satisfying $\nabla f(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r}) = 0$, where $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r})$ stands for the unit normal vector of the surface at position \mathbf{r} . Interbasin surfaces (IBS) dissect the whole molecular space into

individual basins, each IBS actually is a bunch of gradient paths derived from a (3,-1) critical points (CP). The interbasin surfaces of compounds **1-4** generated by (3,-1) critical points are illustrated below.

Figure 3: Plots of the interbasin surfaces of compounds **1-4**

The number of interbasin surfaces is 36, 40, 46 and 49 for compounds **1-4** respectively.

Frontier Molecular Orbitals (FMOs)

Molecular orbitals (HOMO-LUMO) and their properties such as energy are very useful for physicists and chemists and are very important parameters for quantum chemistry. The HOMO energy characterizes the ability of electron giving and

LUMO characterizes the ability of electron accepting and the gap characterizes the molecular chemical stability. The HOMO and LUMO orbitals of compound **4** with a small energy gap were computed by the DFT/B3LYP method with 6-31G (d,p) basis set and visualized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. HOMO-LUMO Structure with the energy level diagram of compound **4**

HOMO-1, LUMO+1 and HOMO are confined over the whole molecule, while LUMO is on (triazolo-thiadiazin-ylidene)hydrazinyl for compound **4** which gives charge transfer process in the molecular system.

Global Reactivity Descriptors

The global reactivity parameters such as chemical hardness, chemical potential and electrophilicity are used for rationalizing, interpreting and predicting

diverse aspects of chemical bonding and reaction mechanism. The calculated values of the global

reactivity descriptors for the title molecules are collected in Table 5.

Table 5. Quantum chemical descriptors of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4**

Parameters	Compound 1	Compound 2	Compound 3	Compound 4
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-6.095	-6.171	-6.160	-6.054
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-2.614	-2.633	-2.610	-2.621
ΔE_{gap} (eV)	3.481	3.538	3.550	3.433
I (eV)	6.095	6.171	6.160	6.054
A (eV)	2.614	2.633	2.610	2.621
μ (eV)	-4.354	-4.402	-4.385	-4.337
χ (eV)	4.354	4.402	4.385	4.337
η (eV)	1.741	1.769	1.775	1.716
S (eV)	0.287	0.283	0.282	0.291
ω (eV)	5.447	5.477	5.415	5.480

The compound which has the lowest energy gap is the compound **4** ($\Delta E_{\text{gap}} = 3.433$ eV). This lower gap allows it to be the softest molecule. The compound that has the highest energy gap is the compound **3** ($\Delta E_{\text{gap}} = 3.550$ eV). The compound that has the highest HOMO energy is the compound **4** ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -6.054$ eV). This higher energy allows it to be the best electron donor. The compound that has the lowest LUMO energy is the compound **2** ($E_{\text{LUMO}} = -2.633$ eV) which signifies that it can be the best electron acceptor. The two properties like I (potential ionization) and A (affinity) are so important, the determination of these two properties allows us to calculate the absolute electronegativity (χ) and the absolute hardness (η). These two parameters are related to the one-electron orbital energies of the HOMO and LUMO respectively. Compound **4** has the lowest value of the potential ionization ($I = 6.054$ eV), so that will be the better electron donor. Compound **2** has the largest value of the affinity ($A = 2.633$ eV), so it is the better electron acceptor. The chemical reactivity varies with the structure of molecules. Chemical hardness (softness) value of

compound **4** ($\eta = 1.716$ eV, $S = 0.291$ eV) is lesser (greater) among all the molecules. Thus, compound **4** is found to be more reactive than all the compounds. Compound **2** possesses higher electronegativity value ($\chi = 4.402$ eV) than all compounds so; it is the best electron acceptor. The value of ω for compound **4** ($\omega = 5.480$ eV) indicates that it is the stronger electrophiles than all compounds. Compound **4** has the smaller frontier orbital gap so, it is more polarizable and is associated with a high chemical reactivity, low kinetic stability and is also termed as soft molecule.

Mulliken analysis

Mulliken atomic charge calculation has an important role in the application of quantum chemical calculation to molecular system [12]. Because the atomic charges affect dipole moment, polarizability, electronic structure and more a lot of properties of molecular systems. The total atomic charges of Compound **4** (the more reactive compound) obtained by Mulliken population analysis with DFT/B3LYP method and 6-31G (d,p) basis set and presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Mulliken's plot of compound **4**

The atom 14N shows more negative (-0.694306e) charge and 11S more positive (1.176193e) charge, which suggests extensive charge delocalization in the entire molecule. The charge noticed on the 32N, 31N, 19N and 28N is smaller and equal to -0.375511e, -0.332744e, -0.284557e and -0.282125e respectively. This can be explained by the high degree of conjugation, with a strong push-pull effect. Negatively charged oxygen (12O, 13O) atoms shows that charge is transferred from sulfur to oxygen. Carbon atom 24C is more negatively charged which indicate that the charge transfer from sulfamide group to methyl group through benzene ring. The negative charge of 17N and 29N is equal to -0.454477e and -0.380533e respectively, which explain that, is due to the most positive charge of 18H and 30C respectively, attached to azote atoms. The maximum atomic charge of carbons is obtained for 4C and 30C. This is due to the attachment of negatively charged azote. The positive charges are localized on the hydrogen atoms. Very similar values of positive

charges are observed for the hydrogen atoms (26H, 18H and 15H (0.140383, 0.291407 and 0.296112e) respectively) bonded to the negative atoms (24C, 17N and 14N) respectively.

Natural Bond Orbital Analysis (NBO)

NBO analysis provides the most accurate possible natural Lewis structure picture, because all the orbital details are mathematically chosen to include the highest possible percentage of the electron density. A useful aspect of the NBO method is that it gives information about interactions in both filled and virtual orbital spaces that could enhance the analysis of intra and inter molecular interactions [13]. The stabilization energy E (2) values of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4** were calculated on the basis of second-order Fock matrix perturbation theory using B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) basis set. The larger E (2) values were listed in Tables 6-9.

Table 6. Second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix on NBO of compound **1**

Donor(i)	ED/e	Acceptor(j)	ED/e	E(2) Kcal/mol	E(j)-E(i) a.u	F(i,j) a.u
LP (1) N11	1.65965	$\pi^*(\text{N19-C20})$	0.32603	46.16	0.26	0.099
LP (1) N29	1.54890	$\pi^*(\text{C22-N32})$	0.37615	42.03	0.29	0.100
LP (1) N29	1.54890	$\pi^*(\text{C30-N33})$	0.28465	36.31	0.30	0.097
LP (1) N11	1.65965	$\pi^*(\text{C3-C4})$	0.39703	35.95	0.31	0.095
LP (1) N29	1.54890	$\pi^*(\text{C21-N28})$	0.20339	26.44	0.28	0.082
π (C3-C4)	1.61636	$\pi^*(\text{C1-C2})$	0.39652	25.88	0.28	0.076
π (C1-C2)	1.67828	$\pi^*(\text{C5-C6})$	0.31313	23.51	0.29	0.074
LP (2) S23	1.79237	$\pi^*(\text{C22-N32})$	0.37615	23.19	0.26	0.072
π (C5-C6)	1.69290	$\pi^*(\text{C3-C4})$	0.39703	22.21	0.28	0.072
LP (3) O14	1.78319	$\sigma^*(\text{S13-O15})$	0.15975	21.74	0.57	0.101
LP (3) O15	1.77801	$\sigma^*(\text{S13-O14})$	0.15380	21.20	0.57	0.100
π (C3-C4)	1.61636	$\pi^*(\text{C5-C6})$	0.31313	16.55	0.28	0.062
LP (2) O15	1.81862	$\sigma^*(\text{C1-S13})$	0.19877	16.19	0.45	0.077
π (C1-C2)	1.67828	$\pi^*(\text{C3-C4})$	0.39703	15.79	0.28	0.061
LP (2) O14	1.81944	$\sigma^*(\text{C1-S13})$	0.19877	15.78	0.45	0.076
π (C5-C6)	1.69290	$\pi^*(\text{C1-C2})$	0.39652	15.70	0.28	0.060
LP (2) S23	1.79237	$\pi^*(\text{N19-C20})$	0.32603	15.48	0.23	0.055
LP (2) O14	1.81944	$\sigma^*(\text{S13-N16})$	0.24451	14.00	0.41	0.069
LP (1) N19	1.90350	$\sigma^*(\text{C20-C21})$	0.06594	13.96	0.80	0.095
π (C22-N32)	1.89696	$\pi^*(\text{C30-N33})$	0.28465	12.76	0.33	0.061

Table 7. Second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix on NBO of compound 2

Donor(i)	ED/e	Acceptor(j)	ED/e	E(2) Kcal/mol	E(j)-E(i) a.u	F(i,j) a.u
LP (1) N29	1.55682	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.37549	41.11	0.29	0.099
LP (1) N29	1.55682	$\pi^*(C30-N32)$	0.29420	36.71	0.31	0.099
LP (1) N29	1.55682	$\pi^*(C21-N28)$	0.18402	26.26	0.28	0.082
π (C4-C5)	1.64402	$\pi^*(C1-C6)$	0.38291	25.23	0.28	0.076
LP (2) S23	1.77043	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.37549	23.24	0.26	0.072
π (C1-C6)	1.69302	$\pi^*(C2-C3)$	0.29480	22.67	0.29	0.073
LP (1) N17	1.78527	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39551	22.39	0.34	0.082
π (C2-C3)	1.69786	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39551	22.14	0.28	0.072
LP (3) O12	1.78425	$\sigma^*(S11-O13)$	0.16154	21.97	0.56	0.101
LP (3) O13	1.77863	$\sigma^*(S11-O12)$	0.15228	20.91	0.57	0.099
LP (2) S23	1.77043	$\pi^*(N19-C20)$	0.24157	17.07	0.24	0.057
LP (2) O13	1.81814	$\sigma^*(C1-S11)$	0.19903	16.38	0.45	0.077
LP (2) O12	1.81796	$\sigma^*(C1-S11)$	0.19903	15.71	0.45	0.076
π (C2-C3)	1.69786	$\pi^*(C1-C6)$	0.38291	15.69	0.28	0.060
π (C4-C5)	1.64402	$\pi^*(C2-C3)$	0.29480	15.60	0.29	0.061
π (C1-C6)	1.69302	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39551	15.17	0.28	0.060
LP (1) N17	1.78527	$\pi^*(N19-C20)$	0.24157	14.58	0.31	0.060
LP (2) O12	1.81796	$\sigma^*(S11-N14)$	0.24448	14.29	0.41	0.069
LP (1) N19	1.92179	$\sigma^*(C20-C21)$	0.06970	13.91	0.79	0.094
π (C30-N32)	1.89342	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.37549	13.02	0.31	0.061

Table 8. Second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix on NBO of compound 3

Donor(i)	ED/e	Acceptor(j)	ED/e	E(2) Kcal/mol	E(j)-E(i) a.u	F(i,j) a.u
LP (1) N29	1.55667	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.37554	41.07	0.29	0.098
LP (1) N29	1.55667	$\pi^*(C30-N32)$	0.28936	36.18	0.31	0.099
LP (1) N29	1.55667	$\pi^*(C21-N28)$	0.18477	26.25	0.28	0.082
π (C4-C5)	1.64357	$\pi^*(C1-C6)$	0.38328	25.26	0.28	0.076
LP (2) S23	1.77186	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.37554	23.03	0.26	0.072
π (C1-C6)	1.69287	$\pi^*(C2-C3)$	0.29510	22.69	0.29	0.073
LP (1) N17	1.78415	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39598	22.56	0.34	0.082
π (C2-C3)	1.69793	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39598	22.14	0.28	0.072
LP (3) O12	1.78403	$\sigma^*(S11-O13)$	0.16127	21.93	0.57	0.101
LP (3) O13	1.77862	$\sigma^*(S11-O12)$	0.15251	20.96	0.57	0.099
LP (2) S23	1.77186	$\pi^*(N19-C20)$	0.24039	16.83	0.24	0.057
LP (2) O13	1.81826	$\sigma^*(C1-S11)$	0.19895	16.35	0.45	0.077
LP (2) O12	1.81818	$\sigma^*(C1-S11)$	0.19895	15.72	0.45	0.076
π (C2-C3)	1.69793	$\pi^*(C1-C6)$	0.38328	15.68	0.28	0.060
π (C4-C5)	1.64357	$\pi^*(C2-C3)$	0.29510	15.60	0.29	0.061
π (C1-C6)	1.69287	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39598	15.16	0.28	0.060
LP (1) N17	1.78415	$\pi^*(N19-C20)$	0.24039	14.70	0.31	0.060
LP (2) O12	1.81818	$\sigma^*(S11-N14)$	0.24449	14.24	0.41	0.069
LP (1) N19	1.92204	$\sigma^*(C20-C21)$	0.06958	13.87	0.79	0.094
π (C30-N32)	1.89435	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.37554	13.07	0.31	0.061

Table 9. Second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix on NBO of compound 4

Donor(i)	ED/e	Acceptor(j)	ED/e	E(2) Kcal/mol	E(j)-E(i) a.u	F(i,j) a.u
LP (1) N29	1.56076	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.38411	40.42	0.29	0.097
LP (1) N29	1.56076	$\pi^*(C30-N32)$	0.33623	36.06	0.31	0.097
π (C4-C5)	1.64476	$\pi^*(C1-C6)$	0.38194	25.07	0.28	0.076
LP (1) N29	1.56076	$\pi^*(C21-N28)$	0.18265	24.80	0.28	0.080
LP (2) S23	1.77050	$\pi^*(C22-N31)$	0.38411	23.27	0.26	0.072
π (C1-C6)	1.69174	$\pi^*(C2-C3)$	0.38194	22.64	0.29	0.073
π (C2-C3)	1.69599	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39468	22.14	0.28	0.072
LP (1) N17	1.77993	$\pi^*(C4-C5)$	0.39468	22.05	0.34	0.081
LP (3) O12	1.78442	$\sigma^*(S11-O13)$	0.16152	21.98	0.57	0.101
π (C36-C40)	1.65508	$\pi^*(C33-C34)$	0.38112	21.31	0.28	0.069
LP (3) O13	1.77842	$\sigma^*(S11-O12)$	0.15224	20.88	0.57	0.099
π (C35-C38)	1.66440	$\pi^*(C36-C40)$	0.32565	20.75	0.28	0.068
π (C33-C34)	1.64479	$\pi^*(C30-N32)$	0.33623	20.16	0.26	0.064
π (C35-C38)	1.66440	$\pi^*(C33-C34)$	0.38112	19.25	0.28	0.066
π (C33-C34)	1.64479	$\pi^*(C35-C38)$	0.29712	19.21	0.29	0.067
π (C33-C34)	1.64479	$\pi^*(C36-C40)$	0.32565	19.20	0.28	0.066
π (C36-C40)	1.65508	$\pi^*(C35-C38)$	0.29712	18.82	0.29	0.066
LP (2) O13	1.81776	$\sigma^*(C1-S11)$	0.19946	16.46	0.45	0.077
LP (1) N17	1.77993	$\pi^*(N19-C20)$	0.24144	16.42	0.30	0.063
LP (2) S23	1.77050	$\pi^*(N19-C20)$	0.24144	16.38	0.24	0.056

The intra molecular interaction for the title compounds is formed by the orbital overlap between: π (C3-C4) and $\pi^*(C1-C2)$ for compound **1**, π (C4-C5) and $\pi^*(C1-C6)$ for compound **2**, compound **3** and compound **4** respectively, which result into intermolecular charge transfer (ICT) causing stabilization of the system. The intra molecular hyper conjugative interactions of π (C3-C4) to $\pi^*(C1-C2)$ for compound **1**, π (C4-C5) to $\pi^*(C1-C6)$ for compound **2**, π (C4-C5) to $\pi^*(C1-C6)$ for compound **3** and π (C4-C5) to $\pi^*(C1-C6)$ for compound **4** lead to highest stabilization of 25.88, 25.23, 25.26 and 25.07 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. In case of LP (1) N11 orbital to the $\pi^*(N19-C20)$ for compound **1**, LP (1) N29 orbital to $\pi^*(C22-N31)$ for compound **2**,

compound **3** and compound **4** respectively, show the stabilization energy of 46.16, 41.11, 41.07 and 40.42 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Nonlinear Optical Properties (NLO)

Molecules with second-order nonlinear optical (NLO) property have received much attention in the recent years as they have found vast applications in the optoelectronic devices of telecommunications, optical fibres, information storage, optical switching and signal processing [14-16]. The dipole moment, polarizability, anisotropy of polarizability and first hyperpolarizability of title compounds were calculated using B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) basis set and determined in Table 10.

Table 10. Nonlinear optical properties of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4**.

Parameters	Compound 1	Compound 2	Compound 3	Compound 4
β_{xxx}	197.3713	-246.7361	-239.0400	-218.3973
β_{yyy}	33.2945	-32.4753	-31.0830	-0.7714
β_{zzz}	5.1068	6.9577	6.0814	2.3146
β_{xyy}	47.7653	-12.6481	-2.2727	13.6896
β_{xxy}	115.8648	-63.3130	-30.3453	27.6427
β_{xxz}	120.4471	-23.6636	-22.3196	-34.0096
β_{xzz}	28.8049	-37.2111	-47.9564	-72.1366
β_{yzz}	1.2147	8.8313	11.5194	10.4879
β_{yyz}	2.5344	19.3138	13.8906	29.0105
β_{xyz}	-34.9796	53.2635	45.5633	34.0877
$\beta_0(\text{esu}) \times 10^{-33}$	350.8872	309.0908	293.5524	279.3666
μ_x	1.4486	-3.3246	-3.6938	-4.5120
μ_y	5.7513	-4.1854	-3.4786	-2.4833
μ_z	2.0769	1.2422	1.5530	2.0596
$\mu(\text{D})$	6.2840	5.4876	5.3062	5.5468
α_{xx}	-187.7483	-171.0856	-178.7577	-178.9437
α_{yy}	-135.5348	-140.0674	-152.4001	-167.6189
α_{zz}	-138.9664	-147.1168	-160.5744	-174.4677
α_{xy}	-27.7717	2.8947	11.6809	22.1996
α_{xz}	23.8461	30.3930	28.8906	22.0172
α_{yz}	0.4834	-2.5628	-7.6710	-11.6222
$\alpha(\text{esu}) \times 10^{-24}$	81.1127	60.0767	60.2988	58.6137
$\Delta\alpha(\text{esu}) \times 10^{-24}$	12.0209	8.9034	8.9363	8.6865

Since the values of the polarizabilities ($\Delta\alpha$) and the hyperpolarizabilities (β_0) of the GAUSSIAN 09 output are obtained in atomic units (a.u.), the calculated values have been converted into electrostatic units (e.s.u.) (for α ; 1 a.u. = 0.1482×10^{-24} e.s.u., for β ; 1 a.u. = 8.6393×10^{-33} e.s.u.). The calculated values of dipole moment (μ) for the title compounds were found to be 6.2840, 5.4876, 5.3062 and 5.5468 D respectively, which are approximately five and six times than to the value for urea ($\mu = 1.3732$ D). Urea is one of the prototypical molecules used in the study of the NLO properties of molecular systems. Therefore, it has been used frequently as a threshold value for comparative purposes. The calculated values of polarizability are 81.1127×10^{-24} , 60.0767×10^{-24} , 60.2988×10^{-24} and 58.6137×10^{-24} esu respectively; the values of anisotropy of the polarizability are 12.0209, 8.9034, 8.9363 and 8.6865 esu, respectively. The magnitude of the molecular hyperpolarizability (β_0) is one of the important key factors in a NLO system. The DFT/6-31G (d,p) calculated first hyperpolarizability value (β_0) of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives are equal to 350.8872×10^{-33} , 309.0908×10^{-33} , 293.5524×10^{-33} and 279.3666×10^{-33} esu. The first hyperpolarizability of title molecules is approximately 1.02, 0.90, 0.86 and 0.81 times than

those of urea (β of urea is 343.272×10^{-33} esu obtained by B3LYP/6-311G (d,p) method). The above results show that only compound **1** might has the NLO applications.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, we carried out the theoretical analysis of 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazine benzenesulfonamide derivatives **1-4** with the DFT/B3LYP method and 6-31G (d,p) basis set. The MEP plot show the negative electrostatic potential regions are mainly localized over the sulfamide function for compound **1** and they are localized over 31N and 32N sites of [1,2,4]-triazole for compounds **2**, **3** and **4** which explains that they are possible sites of electrophilic attack. The positive regions are localized over all the hydrogen atoms which explain that they are possible sites for nucleophilic attack. The lowering of HOMO-LUMO energy gap clearly explains the charge transfer interactions taking place within the molecule. In addition, computational results from reactivity descriptors for title compounds show that Compound **4** has the smaller frontier orbital gap so; it is the most reactive compound. Mulliken charge analysis also supports the conjugation effect. The electric dipole moment, polarizabilities and the hyperpolarizabilities of the compounds **1-4** show that the title molecules is not an

attractive object for future studies of nonlinear optical properties and only compound **1** exhibited good NLO property and was much greater than that of urea.

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